

STAV360: A Dataset for Subjective Tile-based Assessment of 360° Videos

Moatasim Mahmoud
Singular Logic
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
15561 Athens, Greece
mmoatasim@singularlogic.eu

Pavlos I. Lazaridis
School of Computing and Engineering
University of Huddersfield
HD1 3DH Huddersfield, U.K
p.lazaridis@hud.ac.uk

Stamatia Rizou
R&D Department
Singular Logic
15561 Athens, Greece
srizou@singularlogic.eu

George K. Karagiannidis
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
54124 Thessaloniki, Greece
Lebanese American University
geokarag@auth.gr

Zaharias D. Zaharis
School of Electrical and Computer
Engineering
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
54124 Thessaloniki, Greece
zaharis@auth.gr

Andreas S. Panayides
VIDEOMICS Group
CYENS Centre of Excellence
Nicosia, Cyprus
a.panayides@cyens.org.cy

Nikolaos V. Kantartzis
School of Electrical and Computer
Engineering
Aristotle University of Thessaloniki
54124 Thessaloniki, Greece
kant@auth.gr

Abstract— Tile-based 360° video streaming has recently emerged as a promising strategy for efficient and flexible 360° video transmission. However, spatial variations in the delivered scene quality, caused by combining different quality levels, can influence the users’ perceptual experience. While several models and datasets have been developed for 360° video quality assessment (360° VQA), none of the available studies consider the spatial quality variation that arises in multi-quality tiled 360° video streaming. To bridge this gap, conducting subjective evaluation experiments for tiled omnidirectional videos is essential for developing reliable tiled 360° VQA models and optimized streaming algorithms. This paper introduces the STAV360 dataset, a dataset for subjective tile-based assessment of 360° videos. The STAV360 dataset consists of six 360° video sequences, each tiled and encoded using twelve different patterns, along with subjective ratings and tracking data of 27 participants. STAV360 reveals interesting patterns in subjective tiled 360° VQA, paving the way for new research opportunities in tile-based 360° video streaming and objective 360° VQA metric models. The STAV360 dataset is publicly available at <https://github.com/SLG-European-Projects/STAV360>.

Keywords—dataset, subjective study, video streaming, video quality assessment (VQA), virtual reality (VR), 360° videos

I. INTRODUCTION

Due to their immersive and engaging nature, virtual reality (VR) and 360° multimedia content are attracting more and more users and are being deployed in a variety of domains. Compared to conventional 2D videos, 360° videos engulf the users and set them in an interactive environment that responds to their head movements. Nonetheless, providing a satisfying smooth experience for VR users requires omnidirectional videos to have high-quality and high resolutions (8K or higher), resulting in a substantial challenge for 360° video streaming. In view of this, tile-based 360° video streaming has become a popular solution that projects the omnidirectional scene into equirectangular format and divides it into rectangular tiles that can be encoded and transmitted independently [1]. Since VR users view only part of the spherical scene at a time, known as their viewport or field of view (FoV), ideally, only a subset of the overall tiles needs to be delivered to them at high quality. Consequently, tiled 360° video streaming can reduce the bitrate requirements

substantially while still delivering adequate quality for the users.

Although tile-based streaming reduces the required resources, it can result in delivering different tiles at different quality levels depending on the available resources, users’ viewports, and streaming algorithms. The resulting spatial variation in the scene quality can subsequently degrade the perceptual users’ experience. This can be especially noticeable in cases of marginal quality contrast between adjacent tiles, forming sharp edges between high-quality and low-quality areas. In recent years, several 360° video datasets have been constructed to be utilized in viewport prediction models, 360° VQA studies, and 360° video streaming [2], [3], [4]. However, there is still a lack of tiled 360° video datasets, especially for VQA studies. Moreover, major improvements have been made in 360° VQA by considering the unique characteristics of omnidirectional videos. For instance, the peak signal-to-noise ratio (PSNR) metric has been adapted to 360° videos to create new metrics such as the spherical PSNR (S-PSNR) [5], and the weighted-to-spherical PSNR (WS-PSNR) [6]. Although the available 360° VQA models are specifically designed to depict the quality of omnidirectional content and provide an improvement over legacy metrics, they are particularly useful in cases of uniform full-frame encoding and do not consider the additional quality degradations emerging from combining different tile qualities.

Despite the advancements made in 360° VQA modeling and tiled 360° video streaming, experiments for subjective evaluation of tiled 360° video quality are yet to be conducted. In view of this, we introduce the STAV360 dataset, the first dataset for subjective tile-based 360° VQA. The STAV360 dataset provides the subjective ratings of 27 participants for 360° videos constructed using different tile encoding patterns. The STAV360 dataset should facilitate more research in tiled 360° VQA and quality-driven tile-based 360° video streaming. The dataset also contains the head movement traces that can be utilized for developing and testing viewport prediction algorithms and conducting viewing behavior analysis studies. In this paper, we present the STAV360 dataset and conduct primary analysis of the collected data and provide new insights towards advancing the area of 360° VQA and tiled 360° video streaming.

II. DATASET CREATION & SUBJECTIVE EVALUATION

This section explains the steps and settings used for creating the STAV360 dataset. We introduce the 360° videos in the dataset, and discuss the video capturing setup, encoding settings, and tile encoding patterns. We also explain the subjective evaluation procedure carried out in this experiment.

A. Capturing of 360° Videos

The 360° videos used to create our dataset were captured using an Insta360 Action Camera X4¹ at 8K resolution (7680 × 4320) and 30fps. The camera settings were set to encode the videos using HEVC/H.265 at the highest possible bitrate (200 Mbps). Since the captured videos are stored at very high bitrates, they can reliably be used as reference sequences in the quality assessment of encoded instances at lower rates. Six videos were captured in different environments, which are depicted in Figure 1. These videos are titled: FeedTheDucks, FootballFreestyling, LycabettusSunset, MuseumOfTheAncientAgora, PiraeusPort, and TempleOfHephaestus.

In addition to the environment considerations for scene selection, it is important to include scenes with different spatiotemporal parameters. Adopting test omnidirectional video sequences that span over a range of spatial and temporal perceptual information helps in assessing the quality impairments, caused by compression, for different expected scenarios. To quantify the spatiotemporal features of the captured videos, we compute the spatial information (SI) and temporal information (TI) metrics [7] of the test video sequences. Table 1 shows the obtained statistical SI-TI information for the six 360° videos in the STAV360 dataset. The mean SI values span from 14.66 (MuseumOfTheAncientAgora) to 32.91 (FeedTheDucks). Meanwhile, the mean TI values are from 0.62 (TempleOfHephaestus) to 3.75 (LycabettusSunset). We avoid sequences with very high TI values as they contribute to cybersickness, which can distress the participants and disturb their perceptual ratings.

B. Tiling and Encoding

In this experiment, we follow a uniform tiling grid size of 10x5 tiles, where each of the resulting tiles is square shaped

and has a resolution of 768x768 pixels. Each tile is then encoded using three quantization parameters (QPs) to make three quality levels: High (QP=22), Mid (QP=32), and Low (QP=42). For each video, a set of twelve tiling patterns are then adopted to construct the test sequences. A visual representation of the tiling patterns is displayed in Figure 2, and they can be described as follows:

- Pattern1_Uniform_Low: Uniform setup of all tiles at the lowest quality level (QP=42).
- Pattern2_Uniform_Mid: Uniform setup of all tiles at the Mid quality level (QP=32).
- Pattern3_Uniform_High: Uniform setup of all tiles at the highest quality level (QP=22).
- Pattern4_Center01: Constructed by assigning Mid quality level to central tiles and Low quality level to other tiles.
- Pattern5_Center02: Constructed by assigning High quality level to central tiles and Low quality level to other tiles.
- Pattern6_Center12: Constructed by assigning High quality level to central tiles and Mid quality level to other tiles.
- Pattern7_GradCenter012: Constructed by assigning High quality level to central tiles that gradually decreases to Low quality.
- Pattern8_Checkerboard01: A checkerboard pattern with alternating Low and Mid qualities in horizontal and vertical directions.
- Pattern9_Checkerboard02: A checkerboard pattern with alternating Low and High qualities in the horizontal and vertical directions.
- Pattern10_Checkerboard12: A checkerboard pattern with alternating Mid and High qualities in horizontal and vertical directions.
- Pattern11_random1: A random pattern with equal probability for each tile to be selected as (Low, Mid, High). Each video has a different randomized pattern than the others.
- Pattern12_random2: Another random pattern constructed similarly to Pattern11.

Figure 1. Snapshots of the 360° videos in STAV360.

¹ <https://www insta360.com/product/insta360-x4>

TABLE 1. SI-TI information for the dataset videos.

Video Title	SI				TI			
	min	max	mean	std	min	max	mean	std
FeedTheDucks	32.28	33.40	32.91	0.25	1.56	1.92	1.69	0.06
FootballFreestyling	26.83	28.20	27.53	0.32	1.78	3.98	2.73	0.65
LycabettusSunset	20.05	20.95	20.51	0.16	2.49	5.09	3.75	0.53
MuseumOfTheAncientAgora	14.29	14.96	14.66	0.16	0.73	2.16	1.30	0.40
PiraeusPort	16.00	16.56	16.32	0.09	0.63	0.97	0.79	0.06
TempleOfHephaestus	24.36	25.20	24.78	0.19	0.33	1.12	0.62	0.18

Figure 2. Tile encoding patterns. Darker colors indicate higher quality.

These patterns were carefully selected to convey a range of scenarios that can emerge in tile-based 360° video streaming and can have different implications on the perceptual quality.

C. Test Procedure

A total of 27 participants (18 male, 9 female) took part in this experiment. Their ages ranged from 18 to 47 years old, where they were mostly university students and young professionals. Throughout the experiment, we followed the recommendations provided by ITU-T P. 919 [8] regarding the criteria of source videos, test environment, etc. Prior to the experiment, the participants were asked to read about the experiment scope and procedure. They were also asked to fill in a short questionnaire. More guidelines about using the VR headset and rating procedure were also explained to them by the experimenter who was present during the test. For each participant, the experiment lasted for approximately 20 minutes. It was divided into 6 content sessions, corresponding to the six videos in the dataset. Each session consisted of 12 video instances, corresponding to the twelve tiling patterns.

The video instances were presented to each participant in a different randomized order. For viewing the 360° videos, the participants used a Meta Quest 3² VR headset while seated on a swivel chair, so they can freely rotate to explore the whole 360° content. To keep the participants immersed in the VR environment, we developed a standalone VR application using the Unity game engine to play the 360° videos and allow the participants to rate their qualities in-app using the Quest controllers, without the need to take off the headset or to communicate their ratings to the experimenter. Once a video instance is finished, the participants were asked to rate its overall visual quality using the VR controller on a scale from 1 to 5 (5. excellent; 4. very good; 3. fair; 2. poor; and 1. bad.). The absolute category rating (ACR) system was followed throughout the experiment to avoid extending the test duration, which can cause fatigue and dizziness to the users and affect their ratings. In the ACR system, illustrated in Figure 3, the participant rates the test sequences without seeing the reference sequence.

² <https://www.meta.com/quest/quest-3>

Figure 3. Illustration of the ACR method followed in the test.

Before starting the formal test, the participants went through a short training session to familiarize themselves with the evaluation method and the interface, and to have a reference of the range of available qualities. The videos used in the training sessions were not used in the formal test and no data was collected from it.

In addition to the collected ratings, the developed software collected the head movement (HM) traces from the Meta Quest 3 device of the participants for each video. The traces were saved as yaw, pitch, and roll angles along with the corresponding video time and video frame. After the completion of the experiment, the participants were asked to fill in additional questions and write their comments on the procedure.

III. DATA ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, we analyze the collected data and discuss the main findings in the experiment.

A. MOS Calculations

In this experiment, ratings were collected using the ACR method, which is a single stimulus method, where video sequences were viewed by the participants one at a time. The video sequences were rated independently based on the perceptual quality on a category scale from 1 to 5 (5. excellent; 4. very good; 3. fair; 2. poor; and 1. bad.). Each of the 27 participants gave his/her rating for each of the 72 video sequences. The distribution of the raw ratings collected from the participants, depicted in Figure 4, shows that “3. fair” was the most given rating and the extreme ratings were the least given. However, since some participants can be more strict or lenient than others, we obtain the z-scores and use them to calculate MOS values, omitting the effect of personal bias on the overall ratings.

Let $r_j^{i,k}$ be the rating provided by participant i for stimulus S_j^k , where j represents the test condition (i.e., tile encoding pattern) for the video in content session k . Therefore, each session contains the distorted sequences of the same reference video. We hence calculate the z-scores as follows:

$$z_j^{i,k} = \frac{r_j^{i,k} - \mu^{i,k}}{\sigma^{i,k}} \quad (1)$$

In equation (1), $z_j^{i,k}$ denotes the z-score corresponding to the given rating $r_j^{i,k}$, where $\mu^{i,k}$ and $\sigma^{i,k}$ are the mean and standard deviation values of the raw ratings given by participant i for all the videos in content session k .

Figure 4. Distribution of raw ratings.

We then rescale the z-scores to lie in the range [0, 100]. The rescaled z-scores, denoted $\hat{z}_j^{i,k}$, are then utilized to obtain the mean opinion scores (MOS) for each video.

$$MOS_j^k = \frac{1}{N_j^k} \sum_{i=1}^{N_j^k} \hat{z}_j^{i,k} \quad (2)$$

N_j^k refers to the number of users who gave their ratings to stimulus S_j^k , and MOS_j^k is the final score for that stimulus.

The calculated MOS values are shown in Table 2. Naturally, Pattern3_Uniform_High resulted in the highest MOS scores for most videos, as it encodes all tiles at the highest quality level. However, the average MOS scores obtained for Pattern6_Center12 and for Pattern10_Checkerboard12 are also comparable to Pattern3, although they both contain tiles of the Mid quality level. All patterns have a marginally better performance than Pattern1_Uniform_Low for most videos. Interestingly, the MOS scores for Pattern8_Checkerboard01 and for Pattern9_Checkerboard02 are close for most videos, meaning that the participants’ ratings were more influenced by the low-quality tiles.

To have a more meaningful comparison, we should also consider the bitrate of the different videos and patterns. Typically, an increase in the video bitrate is expected to result in higher perceived quality. However, the relationship between the two is not necessarily straightforward and can sometimes be misleading, especially in the case of tiled 360° videos.

TABLE 2. MOS scores for all 360° videos and tile encoding patterns.

Video Title \ Encoding Pattern	Feed The Ducks	Football Freestyling	Lycabettus Sunset	MuseumOf The AncientAgora	Piraeus Port	TempleOf Hephaestus
Pattern1_Uniform_Low	41.50	41.50	38.74	36.52	39.85	37.01
Pattern2_Uniform_Mid	58.33	62.38	62.21	61.01	63.23	60.74
Pattern3_Uniform_High	71.12	68.29	69.29	70.81	61.28	68.17
Pattern4_Center01	49.04	49.71	45.87	48.78	57.53	52.57
Pattern5_Center02	50.62	52.71	48.87	47.28	59.41	63.40
Pattern6_Center12	62.38	65.55	64.97	67.90	63.97	63.46
Pattern7_GradCenter012	58.66	61.79	60.46	53.76	59.40	60.98
Pattern8_Checkerboard01	42.10	45.40	48.10	48.61	45.84	44.87
Pattern9_Checkerboard02	42.46	49.64	48.33	55.25	52.09	46.66
Pattern10_Checkerboard12	59.45	69.06	67.94	67.42	65.95	64.14
Pattern11_random1	60.55	47.15	56.34	50.08	48.40	60.97
Pattern12_random2	64.39	54.94	49.15	53.13	43.70	37.62

Figure 5. Comparison between tile encoding patterns.

In view of this, we explore the influence of bitrate and tile encoding patterns on the perceived quality of 360° videos. In Figure 5, we plot the MOS scores of the different patterns, averaged for all videos, against the average video bitrate resulting from each pattern. Many important remarks with implications on storing and streaming 360° videos can be made by observing this figure. First, we note that a substantial bitrate reduction of 19% to 29% can be achieved by adopting Pattern6_Center12 or Pattern10_Checkerboard12, at the cost of slight degradation in the perceived quality, compared to Pattern3_Uniform_High. Moreover, some patterns with similar bitrates resulted in marginal difference in MOS scores. For instance, Pattern2_Uniform_Mid and Pattern7_GradCenter012 provided significantly better subjective qualities compared to Pattern9_Checkerboard02 and the two random patterns (Pattern11_random1 and Pattern12_random2). This can be attributed to the high spatial variations in tile quality levels of the latter group. Similarly, Pattern4_Center01 and Pattern5_Center02 result in better MOS scores compared to Pattern8_Checkerboard01. In addition to the influence of spatial quality variations, we note that patterns with higher quality tiles in central areas (i.e., patterns 4, 5, 6, and 7) were given high ratings, as these patterns prioritize tiles that are generally more viewed than the rest of the scene.

B. Analysis of Viewing Behavior

Analyzing user viewing behavior while watching 360° videos helps in understanding user engagement, which can be crucial for developing 360° VQA models and for optimizing viewport-based 360° video streaming performance. VR users tend to navigate omnidirectional videos in specific repeated patterns [2]. While they are free to view any part of the spherical scenes, they mostly choose to focus on central areas of the video frame, especially in the vertical axis. While horizontal explorations can be frequent, vertical HMs are usually limited. This can be attributed to the absence of engaging content near the ‘poles’ of typical real-life 360° videos. Moreover, some videos can be characterized by distinct engaging regions or moving objects that can draw users’ attention and shape their viewing behavior.

In our experiment, we developed the VR software to record the HM traces, taken from the head-mounted display (HMD) device, while the participants are watching the 360° videos. Figure 6 shows the heatmaps generated from the participants’ viewing data for the six videos in the STAV360 dataset. Some interesting patterns can be identified by observing the heatmaps in this figure. First, horizontal navigation is evidently more dominant than vertical navigation for all the test sequences, where the participants mostly viewed content along the horizontal axis. Moreover, some areas of interest can be found in some of the videos where most of the participants’ attention was directed. These areas can be mapped to specific objects in the videos that justify such behavior. This can be best seen in the TempleOfHephaestus sequence, where the participants focused on the people passing and interacting with a cat present in the scene. A similar instance can be also detected in the FeedTheDucks video, where the multiple areas of interest represent different groups of ducks in the scene. In the FootballFreestyling video, the focus was mostly on the performer at the center of the video frames. Different from these examples is the LycabettusSunset video. As it portrays a scenery view with no distinct objects of interest, the viewing traces are almost uniformly distributed in areas around the horizontal axis.

Figure 6. Heatmaps of the viewing directions collected from all participants.

In addition to the video content, the scene navigation can be affected by the quality of viewed areas. In this experiment, we also analyze how VR users interact with tiled 360° videos with tiles encoded at different quality levels. When asked after the experiment, 14 out of 27 participants (~52%) reported that their viewing directions were occasionally influenced by the tiles' qualities, as they focused more on areas of higher quality. It is also worth noting that majority of the other participants reported that they noticed the spatial quality changes which affected their perception of the videos but did not necessarily decide their viewports. Nonetheless, when analyzing the viewing traces of these groups, and how they responded to different tile encoding patterns, we found that participants were rarely discouraged from viewing the lower quality parts. Even for patterns with clear quality contrast areas (e.g., Pattern5_Center02), the overall viewing data was consistent with other patterns. However, since our experiment is mainly designed for subjective quality assessment, more experiments should be held to focus on viewing behavior in tiled 360° videos. Such experiments should contain video instances with longer durations and wider quality ranges, where the users watch the videos normally without being focused on quality rating.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this article, we introduced the STAV360 dataset, the first 360° VQA dataset dedicated to the subjective quality of tiled 360° videos. The STAV360 dataset contains six reference 360° videos, where each is encoded using twelve tile encoding patterns. It also provides subjective ratings and head tracking data collected from 27 VR users. We also calculated and analyzed the MOS scores and compared the subjective quality of different tile encoding patterns. We demonstrated that, in addition to individual tile quality levels, spatial variations in tile qualities have a substantial impact on the perceived quality. The dataset and findings of this work

lay the foundation for further research on quality-aware tiled 360° video streaming. In our future work, we plan to utilize the STAV360 dataset to develop novel objective 360° VQA models that incorporate the spatial relationship in tile quality levels for more accurate estimations.

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